

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF EDUACTION TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING - LEARNING ANDEVALUATION

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Abstract.

This study aimed to provide an organised overview of empirical research in the developing subject of educational technology professional development (ETPD) for faculty members. Ensuring the use of technology in the classroom with pedagogical soundness is the main goal of faculty members' ETPD. A comprehensive review of the literature yielded 35 papers. The findings indicated three potential stances that faculty members could use to advance their ETPD: faculty as researcher, faculty as designer, and faculty as learner. By providing empirical evidence, our findings may assist policymakers and stakeholders in understanding the critical indicators of faculty members' ETPD and facilitating a scalable and long-lasting shift in education.

Introduction

Teaching, Learning and Evaluation is one of the most important components of NAAC Assessment and Accreditation for affiliated colleges. The performance of the college in the teaching and learning process and in the evaluation of student performance objectively, transparently, timely and continuously, will be perceived by the stakeholders to form an opinion on the college as compared to other colleges. Considering the special importance of this criterion in the assessment of the quality of an affiliated college, NAAC gave the highest weightage (350 out of 1000) out of all the seven assessment criteria. The affiliated colleges have to reach effectively all the stakeholders in their respective catchment areas with all the information related to the college and admission details. They should have a transparent admission process providing due share to the reservation categories following inclusive policy.

The diverse needs of the students shall be addressed strategically to ensure all the students find a personalized approach in the teaching and learning process. The faculty working in the college should be of high quality and upskill themselves from time to time. They should be empowered to take suitable decisions to achieve optimum results in their work. The teaching and learning methods adopted by the faculty should reflect the changing needs of the students. Advanced teaching methods such as experiential learning, participative learning and other self-learning methods shall be used to make teaching and learning simple and effective. Technology interventions should be integrated into the process to prepare the students for future-ready. The entire system and processes shall be student-centric. The evaluation system should be designed in such a way that it measures the outcomes of the course/programme. There shall be a mechanism to address the grievances of the students on the evaluation. The satisfaction of the students is of vital importance and the colleges should ensure that in all of its academic and administrative activities. Affiliated colleges should study carefully the key indicators of quality in this criterion and evolve policies, procedures, practices and special activities to ensure the highest quality in this. The following are the key indicators of this criterion.

Key indicators of the Criteria:

The key indicators of the teaching, learning and evaluation are; (1) student enrolment and profile, (2) Student –Teacher Ratio, (3) teaching-learning process, (4) teacher profile and quality, (5) evaluation process and reforms, (6) student performance and learning outcomes, (7) student satisfaction and survey.

Key Indicators (KIs)	Affiliated/ Constituent Colleges
2.1 Student Enrolment and Profile	40
2.2 Student Teacher Ratio	40
2.3 Teaching-Learning Process	40
2.4 Teacher Profile and Quality	40
2.5 Evaluation Process and Reforms	40
2.6 Student Performance and Learning Outcomes	90
2.7 Student Satisfaction Survey	60
Total	350

The following paragraphs describe the importance of each of the key indicators:

a. **Student Enrolment and Profile:** The process of admitting students to the programmes is through a transparent, well-administered mechanism, complying with all the norms of the concerned regulatory/governing agencies including state and central governments. Apart from the compliance to the various regulations, the institution put forth its efforts in ensuring equity and wide access having representation of student community from different geographical areas and socio-economic, cultural and educational backgrounds. These will be reflected in the student profile. It is desirable to have students from diverse segments be it gender, region, social class, other states, international students, etc., to reflect holistic and inclusive student population learning and understanding many similarities and differences among themselves.

b. **Student Teacher Ratio:** The new National Education Policy (NEP 2020) calls for significant transformations in all sectors of education. It proposes several changes in the current system aimed at ensuring the provision of quality teachers and quality teaching in order to secure quality education for all. The policy acknowledges teachers

as the heart of the learning process, and stresses the importance of their recruitment, continuing professional development, work environment and service conditions. The policy takes a systems view of teaching quality, linking it to the status

of the profession, the quality of those entering into it, quality of initial professional development, career management and work-place environment including the physical environment, accountability and leadership," the report states. Some of the key recommendations of NEP 2020 directly address solutions the report mentions.

Like the extensive use of technology to improve teaching, learning, educational planning and management; a light but tight regulatory framework to ensure integrity, transparency and effective resource management, and to encourage efficiency of the educational system, innovation and out-of-the-box ideas; research for the sector; and continuous review of progress based on sustained research and assessment. The Student Teacher Ratio (STR) is closely related to quality of teaching, learning and evaluation process. The Student-teacher ratio should be optimal to enable teachers to pay individual attention to students to analyze their interests and competence, their learning process, the outcomes and also contribute significantly for student achievements.

c. Teaching-Learning Process: Diversity of learners in respect of their background, abilities and other personal attributes will influence the extent of their learning. The teaching-learning modalities of the institution are rendered to be relevant for the learner group. The learner-centered education through appropriate methodologies such

as participative learning, experiential learning and collaborative learning modes, facilitates effective learning. Teachers provide a variety of learning experiences, including individual and collaborative learning. Interactive and participatory approaches, if employed, create a feeling of responsibility in learners and make learning a process of construction of knowledge. Of late, digital resources for learning have become available and this makes learning more individualized, creative and dynamic.

d. Teacher Profile and Quality: “Teacher quality” is a composite term to indicate the quality of teachers in terms of their qualification, teacher characteristics, adequacy of recruitment procedures, faculty availability, professional development and recognition of teaching abilities. Teachers take the initiative to learn and keep abreast with the latest developments, innovate, continuously seek improvement in their work, and strive for individual and institutional excellence. Acquiring research degrees is

highly desirable. Updating knowledge by participating in training programmes, conferences, workshops and seminars, improving educational qualifications in relevant areas particularly in digital skills and 21st-century skills are important indicators of Teacher quality.

e. Evaluation Process and Reforms: This Key Indicator looks at issues related to the assessment of teaching, learning and evaluative processes and reforms, to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the system. One of the purposes of evaluation is to provide development-inducing feedback. The qualitative dimension of evaluation is in its use for enhancing the competence of students. The innovative evaluation process is to gauge the knowledge and skills acquired at various levels of the programmes. The

quality of the assessment process in an HEI depends on how well the examination system actually tests the Programme outcomes (POs) and Course Outcomes (Cos), quality of questions, the extent of transparency in the system, the extent of development inducing feedback system, regularity in the conduct of examinations and declaration of results as well as the regulatory mechanisms for prompt action on possible errors.

f. Student Performance and Learning Outcomes: The real test of the extent to which teaching-learning has been effective in an HEI is reflected in student performances. Student performance shall be analysed in terms of the realization of learning outcomes which are specifications of what a student should be capable of doing on successful completion of a course and/or a programme. This is the reason for allocating high weightage points to this key indicator in this criteria. The institutions are expected to design an assessment system capable of monitoring the progress of the student in each of the listed outcomes by adopting varied methods and different timelines.

g. Student Satisfaction Survey: All the efforts of teachers and the institution to make learning a meaningful process can be considered impactful only to the extent students perceive it to be meaningful. Their satisfaction level is decided by the kinds of experiences they undergo, the extent of the “comfort” feeling as well as intellectual stimulation the learning situations provide. Their feedback significantly showcases the actual quality of teaching-learning process enabling identification of the strengths of teaching as well as the possible improvements. Student satisfaction, thus, is a direct indicator of the effectiveness of teaching-learning in the institution. It may

be impractical to capture this aspect from every student; however, every HEI can resort to a sample survey on a formalized basis to capture this significant feature. This is the reason the revised assessment framework of NAAC adopts a survey of student satisfaction.

Evaluation Process and Reforms: (Weightage 40)

The issues related to assessment of teaching, learning and evaluative processes and reforms, to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the system are of paramount importance for higher education institution. One of the purposes of evaluation is to provide development-inducing feedback. Further it should also help the teacher to plan appropriate activities for enhancing student performance. The qualitative dimension of evaluation is in its use for enhancing the competence of students. Innovative evaluation process is intended to gauge the knowledge and skills acquired at various levels of the programmes. The major evaluation reforms defined by the university that are adopted by the institutions, and the reforms initiated by the institution's on its own, details on some of the formative and summative evaluation approaches adopted to measure student achievement which have positively impacted the system, details on the significant improvements made in ensuring rigor and transparency in the internal assessment and weightages assigned, for the overall development of students should be rigorously considered. The continuous evaluation during the semester period is a key aspect in the evaluation of the student. This mechanism allows for incremental feedback to identify problems at their earliest stages. Continuous assessment provides students with a constant stream of opportunities to prove their mastery and sends the message that everyone can succeed if given enough time and practice. This reduces the anxiety around testing and

heightens the emphasis on the learning itself. The advanced students can progress through.

DEFINITIONS AND PRELIMINARIES USED IN THIS PAPER:

1. Formula:

$$C_0 = \frac{AE + AI}{W} \times SF \text{ and } P_0 = \text{Average of course out comes}$$

Where AE: (Average of external marks)

AI: (Average of internal marks)

SF : (Syllabus completion factor)

W: (Weight age of marks)

Terms and conditions for defining (CO' s) course out comes :

1. IF $C_0 > 70$, then highest level of course is attained denoted by L_3 .
2. IF $50 < C_0 < 70$, then moderate level of course is attained denoted by L_2 .
3. IF $35 < C_0 < 50$, then average level of course is attained denoted by L_1 .
4. IF $C_0 < 35$, then poor level of course is attained denoted by L_0 .

Terms and conditions for defining (PO's) Programme outcomes :

1. IF $80 < P_0 < 100$, then highest level of programme is attained denoted by grade A.
2. IF $60 < P_0 < 80$, then moderate level of programme is attained denoted by grade B.
3. IF $40 < P_0 < 60$, then average level of programme is attained denoted by grade C.
4. IF $P_0 < 40$, then poor level of programme is attained denoted by grade D.

2. Main Results:

In this Section of the paper, we will calculate OBL , CO' s and PO's of the date which we collect from [4]

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Student Details
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BG 4th Semester(Batch 2019) ▼

Get Course / Subject Statistics

Search Student by Name Search Student by Class Roll No

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Course / Subject Statistics of BG 4th Semester(Batch 2019)

Course Statistics

course	total
BA	230
BBA	50
BCA	12
BCOM	29
BSC	20

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT	FMG417	50	View All	Course Outcome
GENERAL ENGLISH	GE419	259	View All	Course Outcome
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT	HRM417	50	View All	Course Outcome
HOME SCIENCE	HSC416	10	View All	Course Outcome
INDIAN MUSIC	MI416	10	View All	Course Outcome
KASHMIRI LITERATURE	KOL416	1	View All	Course Outcome
MATHEMATICS	MM416	2	View All	Course Outcome
PHYSICS	PH416	2	View All	Course Outcome
PRODUCTION AND OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT	POM417	50	View All	Course Outcome
PERSIAN LITERATURE	PRL416	3	View All	Course Outcome
POLITICAL SCIENCE	PS416	13	View All	Course Outcome
PSYCHOLOGY	PSY416	24	View All	Course Outcome
SOCIOLOGY	SO416	142	View All	Course Outcome
STATISTICS	ST416	3	View All	Course Outcome
STATISTICS	ST417	12	View All	Course Outcome
SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	SME417	12	View All	Course Outcome
TOURISM AND TRAVEL MANAGEMENT	TTM419	2	View All	Course Outcome
URDU LITERATURE	URL416	12	View All	Course Outcome
ZOOLOGY	ZO416	20	View All	Course Outcome

Subject Statistics of BG 4th Semester(Batch 2019)

Course out come for 4th semester (batch -2019) for some specific subjects is as follow:

1. course outcome for BO416

SubjectCode	Total	Calculated	Average
BO416	16	13	73.15

Enter Max. Marks: 90

Percentage of Syllabus Covered: 100

Calculate

Course Outcome for BO416 :: 81.28 %

Here course outcome for BO416 is 81.28%, that is $C_0 > 70$, then highest level of course is attained L_3 .

2. course outcome for HCT416

SubjectCode	Total	Calculated	Average
HCT416	2	1	45

Enter Max. Marks: 90

Percentage of Syllabus Covered: 100

Calculate

Course Outcome for HCT416 :: 50 %

Here course outcome for HCT416 is 50%, that is $C_O < 70$, then moderate level of course is attained L_2

3. course outcome for CA416

Course Outcome for CA416 Semester 4 Batch 2019

SubjectCode	Total	Calculated	Average
CA416	3	3	40.33

Enter Max. Marks
80

Percentage of Syllabus Covered
100

Calculate

Course Outcome for CA416 :: 44.81 %

Here course outcome for CA416 is 44.81%, that is $C_O < 50$, then moderate level of course is attained L_1 .

4. course outcome for MM416

Course Outcome for MM416 Semester 4 Batch 2019

SubjectCode	Total	Calculated	Average
MM416	2	2	40

Enter Max. Marks
80

Percentage of Syllabus Covered
100

Calculate

Course Outcome for MM416 :: 44.44 %

Here course outcome for MM416 is 44.44%, that is $C_0 < 50$, then average level of course is attained L_1 .

5. course outcome for PH416

Course Outcome for PH416 Semester 4 Batch 2019

SubjectCode	Total	Calculated	Average
PH416	2	2	55.5

Course Outcome for PH416 :: 61.67 %

Here course outcome for PH416 is 61.67%, that is $C_0 > 50$, then moderate level of course is attained L_2 .

CONCLUSION:

Conducting this literature review has given us the opportunity to explore ETPD in higher education through a diversity of methodologies and theories, navigating through several educational contexts in different areas of the world since 2002. Following our immersion in this emerging field of research, we conclude by attempting to illuminate some key insights and suggest some prospects for future inquiry. A first glance at our literature review demonstrates that AngloSaxon countries prevail (see Table 1), which may be explained by the bias toward English language publications. However, the Netherlands has stood out since the beginning of this emerging research field. In fact, in common with Anglo-Saxon countries, the Netherlands has implemented early national policies, which have brought up faculty ETPD in research agendas earlier than elsewhere. As noted by Drent and Meelissen

(2008), “since the mid-1990’s, the Dutch government has provided teacher education institutes with special facilities to play a pioneering role in the integration of ICT in education” (p. 187). The same facilitating national educational context can be found in the USA where the Department of Education initiated the Preparing Tomorrow’s Teachers to Use Technology program in 1999. In Australia, Romeo et al. (2012) indicated that the Australian National Teaching Teachers for the Future program has engendered research opportunities based on its purpose to build the ICT education capacity of the next generation of teachers. These “pioneer” countries first investigated the field at the individual scale (Dolk et al., 2002), then at the one-to-one (Matthew et al., 2002) and community scales (Maor, 2006). They were followed by “newcomer” countries including Spain (García and Roblin, 2008), Canada (Shattuck and Anderson, 2013), South Africa (Esterhuizen et al., 2013), Kenya (Foley and Masingila, 2014), Turkey (Baran, 2016), Israël (Baya’a and Daher, 2015), United Arab Emirates (Psiropoulos et al., 2016), Belgium (Becuwe et al., 2017), Greece (Psycharis and Kalogeria, 2017), and Taiwan (Chen et al., 2018). These countries offered the opportunity to extend our knowledge in this field of research to different geographical and cultural areas and, therefore, to different educational contexts. From a theoretical perspective, the first works in the field were based on technology, and a major trend toward innovation-based theoretical frameworks then took the lead in all pioneer countries. Finally, beginning in 2013, we noticed an increasing number of international collaborations to investigate faculty ETPD. For example, authors from three different countries (USA, Netherlands, and Belgium) collaborated in Becuwe et al. (2017) study. Conducting this literature review has allowed us to follow the emergence and worldwide spread of an emerging field of research demonstrating that a wide range of theoretical and methodological approaches have been adopted.

Whatever theoretical approaches researchers adopted in this field of knowledge (i.e., technology-based, innovation-based, or socio-cultural interactions-based), they share the same vision of a sustainable and scalable educational change, enabling faculty members to achieve the new educational requirements of the twenty-first century. Niederhauser et al. (2018) defined sustainability and scalability, respectively, as “a persistent and ongoing change of the educational culture” (p. 509) and as “the likelihood that an innovation will diffuse effectively across a culture/context” (p. 511). This review may help inform stakeholders and policy makers to promote a sustainable and scalable educational change by highlighting key markers of faculty ETPD from empirical evidence. The need to reframe faculty members’ pedagogies toward a more student-centered constructivist approach is one of the key markers (e.g., Ashton and Newman, 2006; Rienties et al., 2013), echoing what we know about the impact on teachers’ pedagogy of technology integration in the classroom (Fishman and Dede, 2016). According to these authors, educational technology should encourage us to rethink the teaching and learning process as a whole and lead beyond what is achievable without it. Therefore, a strong and authentic feeling of transformation in faculty’s own practice is considered a valuable criterion of success for ETPD programs (García and Roblin, 2008). Some authors have also highlighted changed attitudes toward ICT (King and Boyatt, 2014; Baya’a and Daher, 2015), a shift of beliefs and perceptions (Psiropoulos et al., 2016), changed roles in the classroom (Esterhuizen et al., 2013), or improved knowledge and competencies in technology-enhanced teaching (Jaipal-Jamani et al., 2018). Another key marker of faculty ETPD is the redesign of the course curriculum (e.g., Matthew et al., 2002). As faculty members become involved in ETPD programs, authors have observed that (1) new resources have been created such as portfolios or videos (Ashton and Newman,

2006; Christ et al., 2017), (2) the number of webbased learning environments, courses on Moodle, and ICT pedagogical initiatives has increased (Baya'a and Daher, 2015), or (3) a wider variety of ways to integrate technology into teaching have been used (Matthew et al., 2002). Finally, perceived impacts on students emerged sparingly as a key marker in our literature review (Archambault et al., 2010; Derting et al., 2016).

This is surprising because students' success should be the

ultimate goal of faculty members' ETPD. Therefore, perceived impacts on students should be used as a basic outcome to improve faculty professional development.

Derting et al. (2016) raised the lack of objective measures of student learning and skills. As we conclude and reflect on this journey in an emerging field of research, we realize that while, on the one hand, we have gained much knowledge about ETPD in higher education,

much uncertainty remains. For example, we do not know (1) if faculty members' postures should be adopted simultaneously or through a developmental process, (2) if these different postures independently affect key markers of ETPD or target specific ones,

or (3) if future research in this field should reach a consensus regarding which theoretical and methodological approach should be adopted in order to build an inclusive framework to study ETPD in higher education within a variety of diverse educational

contexts. We suggest design-based implementation research (Fishman and Dede, 2016) to be this inclusive framework as it will help (1) understand faculty members ETPD beyond the three separate main postures we identified, (2) consider sustainability and scalability as key issues from the beginning of the design process,

and (3) focus at the level of schools or school systems as opposed to at the level of a single classroom or group

of classrooms. Finally, conducting a systematic literature review in ETPD in higher education brings out some limitations related to an emerging field of research including potential number of papers that may be included, diversity of research investigations, and dealing with a rapidly changing technology world that impacts research inquiries. However, this attempt to synthesize in a meaningful way research in ETPD in higher education may offer to the research community the opportunity to build their investigations on what we already know in this emerging field of research in order to explore what remains to be discovered.

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